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IRRAD Data Manager Technical Report

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Summary

This document dives into the technical details of the IRRAD Data Manager (IDM), with the intent of easing the introduction phase of future software developers. Contents include the technology stack, application architecture, data models, development environment, coding style guides, usability testing and project management.

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1 Introduction

1.1 IRRAD

IRRAD is a proton irradiation facility located at the East Area of the CERN Proton Synchrotron (PS) accelerator. The primary proton beam is delivered from the PS accelerator with a momentum of 24 GeV/c.

Figure 1: IRRAD as part of CERN's accelerator schema.

Figure 2: Layout of IRRAD facility.

Figure 3: IRRAD bunker external view.

IRRAD has nine irradiation tables and a shuttle where samples can be placed for irradiation. The IRRAD tables are motorized and are capable of placing and removing samples from the beam area remotely[1]. The shuttle is also motorized and can be used to insert samples in the beam area without accessing the irradiation bunker physically and therefore without interrupting irradiations. An example of an IRRAD table prepared for irradiation is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Example of IRRAD table prepared for irradiation.

The facility is also equipped with a cryostat to simulate low temperature irradiation conditions, such as the ones present in CERN’s accelerators.

With all the aforementioned equipment and infrastructure, IRRAD is capable of performing a wide variety of accelerated radiation experiments, playing a key role in the development of CERN’s particle accelerators.

For more information on the IRRAD facility, it is possible to read the IRRAD Long Shutdown 2 (LS2) upgrade paper [2]. Also there is additional information in the CERN IRRAD website [3].

1.2 Project Objective

In the last years IRRAD has experienced an increase in irradiation experiments. Figure 5 shows the progression of irradiation experiments since 2008.

Figure 5: IRRAD number of protons delivered (red), number of samples irradiated in experiments (black), number of proton irradiation days (blue), and number of heavy ion irradiation days (green). All values are accumulated values per year. Graph data interruptions represent both CERN’s Long Shutdown 1 (LS1) from 2012 to 2013 and Long Shutdown 2 (LS2) from 2018 to 2021. Dotted lines represent data before LS1, and continuous lines data between LS1 and LS2.

The increasing volume required new tools to aid the IRRAD team on a daily basis. The

IRRAD Data Manager (IDM) is a web application developed to help in this regard, and designed specifically for the operation of the IRRAD proton facility.

IDM serves two main purposes at the IRRAD facility. First, it works as a data management system storing information related to irradiation experiments. Second, it standardizes and automates irradiation experiment tasks, such as experiment registration, fluence estimation, dosimetry result delivery and more. Figure 6 shows the sequential phases identified in proton irradiation experiments used to design IDM. These phases are explained below.

Figure 6: Irradiation experiment phases before, during and after irradiation.

1. **Registration:** This phase requires experiment users to provide the necessary information to the IRRAD team to evaluate the experiment’s feasibility. This information includes a brief description, the requested fluence for the experiment, availability, number of samples to be irradiated, materials and contact information.
2. **Planning:** Once the IRRAD team has determined if the experiment is feasible using preliminary information, further information is necessary to perform the experiment, such as sample size, layer and composition, traceability and transportation information. With this information the IRRAD team can prepare everything up to the execution of the irradiation.
3. **Operation:** With the experiment in place the irradiation can start. The operation phase represents the irradiation of samples, from beginning to end. Once started the irradiation of samples, when time comes, samples are removed from the irradiation bunker and stored to cool down and reduce their radioactivity.
4. **Dosimetry:** After cooling down, samples undergo a dosimetry radiation measurement to calculate precisely the radiation to which they have been exposed. This measurements can be performed using the IRRAD team’s spectrometers.
5. **Traceability:** For the transportation of radioactive samples, the IRRAD team has to coordinate with the Radiation Protection Group to ensure all samples are traced before being safely transported to their destinations.

6. **History:** Lastly, completed experiments are added to a historic record and used as reference for future experiments.

The objectives of IDM are to manage experimental data and standardize and automate as much as possible the workflow phases of proton irradiation's experiments described above.

1.3 Project Code

The IRRAD team has prepared a specific version of the project's code for public access. The version of the project code referenced in this document can be found in the following [link](#). The code is hosted in CERN's GitLab servers.

1.4 Technologies

Figure 7 shows the technology stack for the project. The project can be subdivided into the front end, back end, development and deployment.

Firstly, for the development, JIRA [4] is used to manage the project and monitor development progress. GitLab [5] is used for version controlling and Selenium [6] for automated functional testing.

Secondly, on the front end, Semantic UI [7] JavaScript and CSS libraries along JQuery [8] power the graphical user interface.

Thirdly, in the back end the Python Django framework [9] is used in conjunction with Oracle databases [10].

Lastly, for the deployment, Openshift [11] and Docker [12] enable the deployment of the application in an isolated environment. Openshift is used to deploy the application to the production and test server. Since Django already includes a development server, Openshift isn't used for the development server.

Figure 7: IDM technology stack.

1.5 File structure

This section goes into detail on the project file structure, to help understand the functionality contained in files and directories.

The project is composed of two Django projects `irrad-data-manager` and `samples_manager`. The former is in charge of the application settings, the Django admin portal and the redirection of requests to `samples_manager`, which is IDM. Figure 8 shows the root folder of the repository, including both projects mentioned before.

In Figure 8 it is visible a SQLite database. This database is used during development since with CERN Oracle databases it is not possible to delete old and create new databases, and this ability is needed by automated tests.

Figure 8: Project root directory.

Figure 9 displays the files available in the `samples_manager` project. The files in the directory are related to the django admin page, forms, fields, urls and views of the application. For further details it is possible to read the file comments.

Figure 9: Application directory.

Now the broad functionality of each directory is explained below:

- **fixtures:** Directory containing fixtures of all data models in the application. Fixtures provide initial data during the initialization of the database. Fixtures are used mainly in automated tests.
- **middleware:** Directory containing application middleware. IDM has middleware for managing timezones. Currently it only handles local server timezones, but it has been structured to easily implement local user-specific timezones.
- **migrations:** Directory containing a history of database changes. Used by Django internally [9].
- **static:** Directory containing all static files referenced in templates. Most of the files belong to front end libraries. To read about the static files developed specifically for IDM, advance to the front end section of this document.
- **templates:** Directory containing all templates used in IDM.

- **templatetags:** Directory containing template filters. Currently only one filter is defined, a filter used to display numbers in decimal and scientific notation.
- **tests:** Directory containing IDM automated tests. The library Selenium is only used for functional automated tests stored in the file test_functional.

1.6 Application Architecture

Figure 10: Schema of IDM production architecture.

Figure 10 is a schema of the IDM application architecture in the production server. This section will explain the components appearing in the diagram.

IDM is deployed using CERN’s OpenShift platform infrastructure. IDM uses OpenShift to host the application and also configure CERN’s Single Sign-On (SSO) system. Once configured, the application is restricted to CERN authorized users. IDM is also deployed by OpenShift in a Docker container to optimize resources and isolate the execution environment.

In operation Django orchestrates the requests to different data sources to build the final HTML responses. Django has to communicate with multiple data sources: the IDM database, Infor EAM database and CERN location database. The IDM database stores all the information regarding present and past IRRAD irradiation experiments. The Infor EAM database stores information regarding the transportation of radioactive material at CERN.

IDM uses this data source to coordinate with the Radiation Protection group regarding the transportation of radioactive material produced during experiments. Lastly, IDM communicates with CERN's location database to retrieve CERN's room codes, which are in total more than 20.000.

To communicate with the Infor EAM services, IDM uses a SOAP interface. To extract the desired information from databases, IDM uses the SQL query language.

1.7 Project Dimension

As of November 2021, the repository stores 581 files with 323.400 lines of code. As shown in Figure 11, most of the files are not being actively developed because they belong to multiple libraries used by IDM. The portion of the repository which the developer will need to understand is only 31,198 lines of code, less than 10% of the total number of lines of code.

To get a sense about how is the actively developed portion of the project, Figure 12 shows the lines of code per file format for the actively developed code. The typical file formats are Python, JavaScript, HTML, CSS and JSON. Python accounts for the majority of lines. This is due to the automated tests, which are over 10k lines of code. HTML code is composed entirely of Django templates and account for 14% of the code. Also JSON files are Django fixtures, which are used during the automated testing.

Figure 11: Actively developed portion of project.

Lines of code per format for development portion of project

Highcharts.com

Figure 12: Lines of code per format for actively developed portion of project.

2 Back End

2.1 Data Models

As seen in Figure 13, the database has 16 different model classes. The two main classes are the class Experiment and Sample classes. They are the central models of the application. The diagram is simplified to only show the model names and their relationships. For a complete diagram of the database see Figure 14.

The models and their attributes are explained in this section one by one.

Figure 13: Simplified database Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD).

Figure 14: Complete database Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD).

2.1.1 Experiment

Experiment is the main class of the application. All samples need to be associated to an experiment, and therefore also all irradiations are also associated to an experiment. Being one of the main classes, it is also one of the biggest.

Name	Description
title	Descriptive main identifier for experiments.
description	Further details beyond title needed by the IRRAD team to evaluate the feasibility of the experiment.
cern_experiment	CERN experiment awaiting irradiation results for analysis.
availability	Date from which it is possible to perform the irradiation.
constraints	Additional details regarding restrictions specific to experiment.
number_samples	Number of samples users expect to irradiate during experiment.
number_registered_samples	Number of samples associated to experiment by users so far.
number_users	Number of users associated to experiment.
radiation_length_occupancy	Percentage out of total IRRAD radiation length capacity. Sum of all associated sample's radiation length occupancy. For information on radiation length see Element class.
nu_coll_length_occupancy	Percentage out of total IRRAD nuclear collision length capacity. Sum of all associated sample's nuclear collision length occupancy. For information on nuclear collision length see Element class.
nu_int_length_occupancy	Percentage out of total IRRAD nuclear interaction length capacity. Sum of all associated sample's nuclear interaction length occupancy. For information on nuclear interaction length see Element class.

Table 1. Experiment model attributes (1/2).

Name	Description
comments	-
category	Three possible categories: Passive Standard, Passive Custom and Active. For details see class descriptions.
regulations_flag	Flag representing the acceptance by users of the terms and conditions of IRRAD irradiations.
irradiation_type	Type of particles wanted to be used in irradiation (e.g. protons, neutrons, ions).
emergency_phone	Emergency phone number to contact in case of emergency.
status	-
responsible	Principal user of experiment.
users	List of users associated to experiment which aren't the responsible.
created_at	Creation timestamp.
updated_at	Last update timestamp.
created_by	User who created instance.
updated_by	User who last updated instance.
public_experiment	Flag representing if experiment is public or not. If public, other IDM users not associated to experiment will be able to see experiment's details.

Table 2. Experiment model attributes (2/2).

2.1.2 Sample

Sample is also a principal class of the application. Samples are composed by layers. They have three dimensions, height, width and length/depth. The length is the aggregate thickness of all the layers.

Samples have a traceability ID used by the Radiation Protection group and IRRAD to track the sample inside and outside the IRRAD facility. Traceability ids follow the following regular expression:

$$r^{\text{SET-}}[0-9]\{6\}$$

Figure 15: Sample set_id regular expression.

Both fluences and materials choices are values defined during the creation of the experi-

ment. Samples can only have one of the values already defined in the experiment.

For information on the values radiation length occupancy, nuclear collision length occupancy and nuclear interaction length occupancy see Occupancy class.

Name	Description
name	Descriptive main identifier for samples.
set_id	Traceability identifier. Used by CERN for the transportation of radioactive materials.
current_location	Last location where sample was located. It must be a CERN room code.
height	-
width	-
weight	-
comments	-
req_fluence	Accumulated fluence by which sample should be retrieved from irradiation area.
material	Type of samples. Available choices are defined during experiment creation.
category	Category of irradiation. Available choices are defined during experiment creation.
storage	Temperature storage. Either room temperature or cold (< 20 Celcius).
status	-
last_location	CERN room code where sample was last located.
experiment	Associated experiment.
box	If applicable, container used for transportation.

Table 3. Sample model attributes (1/2).

Name	Description
radiation_length_occupancy	Percentage out of total IRRAD radiation length capacity. For information on radiation length see Element class.
nu_coll_length_occupancy	Percentage out of total IRRAD nuclear collision length capacity. For information on nuclear collision length see Element class.
nu_int_length_occupancy	Percentage out of total IRRAD nuclear interaction length capacity. For information on nuclear interaction length see Element class.
created_at	Creation timestamp.
updated_at	Last update timestamp.
created_by	User who created instance.
updated_by	User who last updated instance.

Table 4. Sample model attributes (2/2).

2.1.3 Dosimeter

Dosimeters are the physical radiation recorders during irradiations. After irradiation, they undergo spectrometry measurements to determine to the highest precision the amount of radiation samples have received.

Just like samples, they become radioactive after irradiations and require to be traced by the Radiation Protection Group using traceability IDs. Dosimeter traceability IDs are similar to the ones samples have. They follow the following regular expression:

$$r^{DOS-[0-9]{6}(\.[0-9]{1,3})}{0,5}\$$$

Figure 16: Dosimeter dos_id regular expression.

Dosimeters are composed of multiple foils. The length of a dosimeter is the aggregate thickness of its foils.

If a dosimeter has a parent dosimeter association, it means it is a part of a larger dosimeter. Sometimes dosimeters need to be divided into pieces, and each piece needs to be traced individually.

Name	Description
dos_id	Traceability identifier. Used by CERN for the transportation of radioactive materials.
responsible	Associated user in charge of dosimeter. IRRAD team member.
current_location	Last location where dosimeter was located. It must be a CERN room code.
length	Aggregate thickness of all foils.
height	-
width	-
weight	-
comments	-
foils_number	Number of foils composing dosimeter.
dos_type	Type of dosimeter used (e.g. aluminium, diamond).
box	If applicable, container used for transportation.
parent_dosimeter	If applicable, previous dosimeter from which this instance was a part.
status	-
last_location	CERN room code where dosimeter was last located.
created_at	Creation timestamp.
updated_at	Last update timestamp.
created_by	User who created instance.
updated_by	User who last updated instance.

Table 5. Dosimeter model attributes.

2.1.4 Box

Boxes are used for the transportation of radioactive material. When multiple small samples need to be transported, it is easier to encapsulate the samples in a container to simplify transportation.

Name	Description
box_id	Traceability identifier. Used by CERN for tracing radioactive materials.
description	Further details needed for the IRRAD team operation.
responsible	Associated user in charge of box. IRRAD team member.
current_location	Current location where box is located. It must be a CERN room code.
last_location	CERN room code where box was last located.
length	-
height	-
width	-
weight	-
created_at	Creation timestamp.
updated_at	Last update timestamp.
created_by	User who created instance.
updated_by	User who last updated instance.

Table 6. Box model attributes.

2.1.5 Irradiation

Irradiations are the pairing of samples and dosimeters which enable measured irradiations at the IRRAD facility. It is one of the most important classes in IDM.

Although the vast majority of irradiations involve both dosimeter and sample, in some special cases such as dosimetry calibration, dosimeters might need to be irradiated individually. For this reason, it is also possible to create irradiation instances with only a dosimeter.

Since this is the class representing IRRAD irradiations, the class stores radiation-related values like the accumulated SEC and fluence. SEC values are used to monitor live progress data during irradiations. SEC values are also used to determine when to stop irradiations. A fluence estimation is derived from SEC values and displayed live with the help of fluence factors. After irradiations are completed, precise fluence measurements are carried using spectrometry equipment. The attributes measured fluence and fluence error are the output of this process.

When samples are too big, to achieve a uniform irradiation, the sample can be "scanned" by the use of the IRRAD tables' scanning function. This means irradiating uniformly the sample by sliding the sample across the beam area, enabling the irradiation of large sample surfaces. This information is stored in the model as the attribute `is_scan`. This information is

important also because it affects the fluence factors used to calculate live estimated fluences. For more information on fluence factors, see class `FluenceFactor` in this section.

Irradiations might be continuations of previous irradiations. In this case fluences must accumulate on top of the previous irradiation measurements. Irradiations which are a continuation of a previous irradiation are associated in the model through the attribute `previous_irradiation`.

Irradiations have four dates. First, introduction of the sample and dosimeter into beam position. Second, the first positive SEC measurement, which equates to the arrival of the first particles. Third, the last positive SEC measurement. Lastly, the physical removal of the sample and dosimeter from the beam position.

Name	Description
sample	If applicable, sample to be irradiated.
dosimeter	Dosimeter going to be irradiated.
previous_irradiation	If applicable, previous irradiation this instance is using as base. Instance will accumulate fluence on top of previous irradiation.
fluence_factor	Factor used to convert from sec measurement to estimated fluence.
comments	-
date_in	Timestamp when sample is put physically in beam position.
date_first_sec	Timestamp of first positive SEC measurement.
date_last_sec	Timestamp of last positive SEC measurement.
date_out	Timestamp when sample is put physically out of beam position.
table_position	Position in IRRAD table where irradiation will occur.
irrad_table	Irrad table where irradiation will occur.
sec	Secondary electron count (SEC). Measurement used to derive estimated accumulated fluence.

Table 7. Irradiation model attributes (1/2).

Name	Description
estimated_fluence	Estimated accumulated fluence derived from SEC measurement. Used to determine when to stop irradiation.
measured_fluence	Accumulated fluence measured via spectrometry.
fluence_error	Error margin for measured fluence.
status	-
dos_position	Position where dosimeter is placed in irradiation table.
is_scan	Flag representing if irradiation is a scanning irradiation. Used for large irradiations where beam area isn't sufficient. Scanning irradiations are matrix configurations where the beam scans cell by cell applying same fluence to each cell.
created_at	Creation timestamp.
updated_at	Last update timestamp.
created_by	User who created instance.
updated_by	User who last updated instance.

Table 8. Irradiation model attributes (2/2).

2.1.6 Compound

A compound is a mixture of elements. It is composed of one or multiple elements. Compounds are used to describe the composition of sample's layers.

Name	Description
name	Descriptive main identifier for compound.
density	-
num_associated_samples	Number of samples associated with compound. Used to prevent and erroneous deletion.

Table 9. Compound model attributes.

2.1.7 FluenceFactor

A fluence factor is used to convert SEC measurements into particle fluence. They are used during the monitoring of ongoing irradiations. Factors vary depending on irradiations scanning status, dosimeter dimensions and IRRAD table.

Factors have a status to determine if they are active or inactive. Only active factors are used for the calculation of fluence estimations.

Name	Description
value	Factor value.
irrad_table	IRRAD table associated with factor.
dosimeter_height	Height of dosimeters compatible with this factor.
dosimeter_width	Width of dosimeters compatible with this factor.
is_scan	Flag representing if factor is intended for scanning irradiations.
status	-
nuclide	Nuclide for which this factor is used.
created_at	Creation timestamp.
updated_at	Last update timestamp.
created_by	User who created instance.
updated_by	User who last updated instance.

Table 10. FluenceFactor model attributes.

2.1.8 User

IDM users. Initially data is automatically populated through CERN's Single Sign-On (SSO) the first time they enter the application. Later on it can be modified by IDM administrators.

Name	Description
email	-
name	-
surname	-
telephone	-
db_telephone	CERN registered telephone.
department	CERN department.
home_institute	CERN associated institute.
role	Type of user in IDM. Admin or standard user.
last_login	Timestamp of latest login.

Table 11. User model attributes.

2.1.9 ArchiveExperimentSample

Samples which are moved from an experiment to another are recorded as part of the old experiment's archive. The attribute named `experiment` is the experiment where sample was moved at the time, not the current experiment of the sample.

Name	Description
timestamp	Timestamp of sample movement.
experiment	Experiment where sample was moved.
sample	Sample which has been moved.

Table 12. ArchiveExperimentSample model attributes.

2.1.10 CompoundElement

Compound elements are the proportion of an element in a compound.

Name	Description
element_type	Associated element.
percentage	Percentage of element in compound.
compound	Associated compound.

Table 13. CompoundElement model attributes.

2.1.11 Element

Elements from the periodic table and radiation properties needed for irradiation experiment analyses.

Attributes with the "pi" prefix are intended for pion experiments.

Name	Description
atomic_number	-
atomic_symbol	-
atomic_mass	-
density	-
min_ionization	Minimum energy deposited by a particle to an element due to particle momentum [13].
nu_coll_length	Mean free path of a particle before undergoing a nuclear reaction, for a given particle in a given medium. The collision length is smaller than the nuclear interaction length because the latter excludes the elastic and quasi-elastic (diffractive) reactions from its definition.
nu_int_length	Mean distance travelled by a hadronic particle before undergoing an inelastic nuclear interaction.
pi_coll_length	Pion-specific nuclear collision length.
pi_int_length	Pion-specific nuclear interaction length.
radiation_length	Mean length to reduce the energy of a particle by the factor $1/e$ [13].

Table 14. Element model attributes.

2.1.12 Layer

Layers contain information about thickness and composition of samples.

Name	Description
name	-
length	Thickness of layer.
compound_type	Compound associated to layer.
sample	Sample where layer belongs.

Table 15. Layer model attributes.

2.1.13 ReqFluence

Requested fluence is the target fluence for a sample. It determines when the sample should be removed from the irradiation area. Requested fluences are declared during the creation of experiments, to later limit the choices during the creation of samples.

Name	Description
req_fluence	Fluence value.
experiment	Experiment to which fluence belongs.

Table 16. ReqFluence model attributes.

2.1.14 Material

Description of material (sample type) going to be irradiated. Information used by the IRRAD team to evaluate feasibility of experiment.

Name	Description
material	Name of material.
experiment	Experiment to which material belongs.

Table 17. Material model attributes.

2.1.15 Occupancy

Occupancy is the percentage out of the total facility capacity a sample occupies in terms of radiation length, nuclear collision length and nuclear interaction length.

Name	Description
radiation_length_occupancy	Percentage of total IRRAD radiation length capacity sample is occupying.
nu_coll_length_occupancy	Percentage of total IRRAD nuclear collision length capacity sample is occupying.
nu_int_length_occupancy	Percentage of total IRRAD nuclear interaction length capacity sample is occupying.
sample	Sample to which instance belongs.

Table 18. Occupancy model attributes.

2.1.16 PassiveStandardCategory

Experiment category. An irradiation not requiring additional live measurements and using standard irradiation areas.

Name	Description
irradiation_area_5x5	Flag indicating if 5x5 irradiation area is appropriate for the experiment.
irradiation_area_10x10	Flag indicating if 10x10 irradiation area is appropriate for the experiment.
irradiation_area_20x20	Flag indicating if 20x20 irradiation area is appropriate for the experiment.
experiment	Experiment where category belongs.

Table 19. PassiveStandardCategory model attributes.

2.1.17 PassiveCustomCategory

Experiment category. An irradiation not requiring additional live measurements and using nonstandard irradiation areas or additional custom setup.

Name	Description
passive_category_type	Temperature at which experiment should be executed.
active_irradiation_area	Custom irradiation area.
active_modus_operandi	Special remarks on the experiment procedure requirements.
experiment	Experiment where category belongs.

Table 20. PassiveCustomCategory model attributes.

2.1.18 ActiveCategory

Experiment category. An irradiation requiring additional live measurements and using nonstandard irradiation areas.

Name	Description
active_category_type	Temperature at which experiment should be executed.
passive_irradiation_area	Custom irradiation area.
passive_modus_operandi	Special remarks on the experiment procedure requirements and also connectivity.
experiment	Experiment where category belongs.

Table 21. ActiveCategory model attributes.

2.2 Views

IDM exclusively uses function views in the back end. Function views are organized in files depending on the model to which they are related as shown in Figure 17, and views related with multiple data models are stored in the "views.py" file.

Figure 17: Application views files.

Function views in the application can be categorized in two types:

- **Action views:** Views related to actions performed in a page. These actions are usually used to modify model instances and the database. It also involves pagination and filtering actions.

- **Non action views:** Views not related to single page actions such as the navigation across pages. These views can be subdivided into detail and list views. A detail view can be for example displaying the details page of an experiment. An example of a list view would be displaying an experiment's samples list. They are visually different, but equal in functionality since both are only displaying database information.

For information on application actions used to modify model instances, see the IDM User Guide [14].

2.3 Templates

Templates are used by the back end of the application to build all the necessary HTML pages. Templates can have parent-child relationships and therefore follow a hierarchical structure. The hierarchy of the application's templates are defined in Figure 18 and explained in this section.

Figure 18: Template hierarchical relation diagram.

In the template structure shown in Figure 18 it is visible how only two categories of templates don't extend other templates, the base template and partial templates. The base template is the root template used by all other templates in the application, and partial templates don't extend other templates because they are inserted. Partial templates include partial lists, used for example in experiment list pages, and forms.

Figure 19: Index page.

Figure 20: Template structural components of index page.

Figure 21: Example list page.

Figure 22: Template structural components of list page.

CEEN Accelerating science Signed in as: a.monoch@cern.ch Sign out Directory

Home Experiments + Info + Help + IRRAD AIDA

IRRAD Data Manager

Home / Experiments / Details CAEN-RFID-Characterization

<p>Title: CAEN-RFID-Characterization</p> <p>Description: Irradiation of CAEN RFID labels.</p> <p>CEEN experiments/Projects: AIDA/monoch-WP4-Task3</p> <p>Availability: Oct 15, 2021</p> <p>Constraints:</p> <p>Number of declared samples: 1</p> <p>Number of registered samples: 2</p> <p>Realization Length Occupancy: 0.026</p> <p>Nuclear Collision Occupancy: 0.01</p> <p>Nuclear Interaction Occupancy: 0.006</p> <p>Responsible person: a.monoch@cern.ch</p> <p>Irradiation type: Protons</p>	<p>Category: Physics Standard</p> <p>Irradiation area: Sd3-einf</p> <p>Fluence: 1.0000E+12 Protons/cm²</p> <p>Type of samples: RFID</p> <p>Discovery results:</p> <p>Created at: Oct 14, 2021, 4:35 p.m.</p> <p>Updated at: Nov 3, 2021, 12:55 p.m.</p> <p>Created by: a.monoch@cern.ch</p> <p>Updated by: a.monoch@cern.ch</p> <p>Public: True</p> <p>Additional comments: Will register future requested fluences later on, while the experiment progresses. This experiment is progressive. If the RFID labels resist they will be irradiated up to higher fluences. First irradiation is only one split.</p>
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Figure 23: Example details page.

Figure 24: Template structural components of details page.

Figures 19, 21 and 23 show three pages which use the majority of templates in the hierarchy displayed in Figure 18. Figures 20, 22 and 24 highlight the template structural information for each type of page. The numerical values assigned to structural components are consistent between images for comparison purposes, since these pages share multiple templates according to the diagram displayed in Figure 18. The role of each template is explained below:

- **base.html:** Defines section 1 and layout information for section 2. These sections are used in all pages because they are the common structure. Section 1 contains login information and application navigation. Section's 2 layout defines the place where content will be placed.
- **base_list.html:** Defines the layout for section 3 and a layout for section 4. Section 3 contains navigation breadcrumbs. Section 4 contains tabs and a table in list pages, and only information in details pages.
- **index.html:** Defines content inside section 2.
- **tab templates:** Tab templates is a category grouping 'base_all_tab_list.html', 'base_filter_tab_list.html', 'base_action_tab_list.html' and 'base_no_tab_list.html'. The purpose for these templates is to define the tab section of list pages. Tab sections can contain actions and filters, one of them or neither, depending on which of the four templates is used. These templates define section 5 and a layout for section 6. Section 5 is the tab section, which at this point it doesn't contain actions. Section 6 is the list table.
- **base_details.html:** Defines a simple layout for section 4.
- **model_list.html:** Defines value of breadcrumb in section 3, actions available in section 5, and the table and pagination for section 6. Section 6 is populated by including another template called 'partial_model_list.html', which contains the table. Pagination

components are also defined in other templates which are also included in this template. With this structure, it is possible to display different list tables while also minimizing the number of lines of code dedicated to templates.

- **model_details.html**: Defines value of breadcrumb in section 3, and the information displayed in section 4. No partial templates are included in this template.

The hierarchical structure of templates has proved to be useful by enabling the reuse of GUI components and the definition of a consistent look for the application.

2.4 Forms

Forms are an important element of the application. There are over 40 forms in total throughout the application. Forms can be composed of one or more pages. Each of the pages is represented with a different form class.

The screenshot shows a multi-page form with three steps: Step 1, Step 2 (active), and Step 3. Step 2 contains several formsets. The first formset is for 'Irradiation type' with a dropdown menu set to 'Protons'. The second is 'Number of samples' with a text input containing 'e.g. 1'. The third is 'Category' with a dropdown menu set to 'Please choose category'. The fourth is 'Requested fluence (protons/cm²)' with two rows of text inputs, each containing 'e.g. 1.234E+15', and a 'Delete' button with an 'x' icon. Below this is an 'Add' button. The fifth is 'Types of sample' with three rows of text inputs, each containing 'e.g. Silicon', and a 'Delete' button with an 'x' icon. Below this is an 'Add' button. At the bottom of the form are 'Previous' and 'Next' buttons.

Figure 25: Example of form with multiple pages and formsets.

Validation of forms differs between single page forms and forms with multiple pages as shown in Figure 25. Validation of single page forms occurs within the validation functions provided by the Django framework [9] in the form class. In the case of multi-page forms the

validation is executed in two stages. As with single page forms, inside the form class. But in addition, for the validation requiring information from multiple pages, inside the view function in charge of the form request. For this reason, besides the form class error messages available in the Django framework, the application also uses alert messages to inform users if there are any missing pieces of information.

Another detail worth highlighting is the use of formsets. Formsets are placed inside other forms (e.g. experiments form) when the submission of a variable number of inputs is needed. To extend the functionality of formsets in accordance to IDM requirements, the JavaScript library 'jquery.formset.js' is used to enable the dynamic expansion of formsets.

For some forms, custom fields and custom widgets are used. These classes are needed to ensure fields are rendered and behave as intended. Custom fields and widgets are defined in the 'fields.py' file.

3 Front End

3.1 JavaScript

3.1.1 File structure

There is a JavaScript file per list page, and all JS files used in list pages follow the same structure. They are organized in three sections. Firstly, the definitions of event handlers. Second, the association of event handlers with events. Lastly, initialization functions. Figure 26 shows the three sections of the file for the compounds.js file.

```
sample_manager > static > p > # compounds.js ...
1 console.log('loaded compounds.js');
2 $(function () {
3
4     /**
5      * Handler for display compound form button. Admin View.
6      */
7     var loadForm = function () {
8         var serialized_checkboxes = $("input[name='checks[]']").serialize();
9
10        var btn = $(this);
11        var url = btn.attr('data-url');
12        var modalID = "#modal-compound";
13        var type = 'get';
14        var dataType = 'json';
15        var data = serialized_checkboxes;
16        var beforeSend = function () {
17            $(modalID).modal({
18                autofocus: false,
19                closable: false
20            });
21        };
22        var success = function (data) {
23            $(modalID + " .modal-content").html(data.html_form);
24            if (data.alert_message)
25                alert(data.alert_message);
26        };
27        formRequest(url, modalID, type, dataType, beforeSend, success, undefined, data);
28    };
29
30    /**
31     * Handler for submit compound form button. Admin view.
32     * @param {Event} event
33     */
34    var saveForm = function (e) {
35        e.preventDefault();
36        var serialized_checkboxes = $("input[name='checks[]']").serialize();
37
38        var form = $(this);
39        var url = form.attr('action');
40        var modalID = "#modal-compound";
41        var type = form.attr('method');
42        var dataType = 'json';
43        var data = form.serialize() + '&' + serialized_checkboxes;
44        var success = function (data) {
45            if (data.form_is_valid) {
46                // Replace partial template
47                $('#partial-template').html(data.html_list);
48            }
49            else {
50                $(modalID + " .modal-content").html(data.html_form);
51            }
52            if (data.alert_message)
53                alert(data.alert_message);
54        };
55        formRequest(url, modalID, type, dataType, undefined, success, undefined, data);
56    };
57
58    //Event listener locators
59    var eventListeners = [
60        // create, update, clone and delete forms
61        {
62            "selector": "body",
63            "event": "click",
64            "childSelector": ".js-load-compound-form",
65            "handler": loadForm
66        },
67        {
68            "selector": "body",
69            "event": "submit",
70            "childSelector": ".js-submit-compound-form",
71            "handler": saveForm
72        }
73    ];
74
75    //Remove and afterwards add event listeners
76    for (item of eventListeners) {
77        $(item.selector).off(item.event, item.handler);
78        $(item.selector).on(item.event, item.childSelector, item.handler);
79    }
80
81    // Activate tabs
82    activateTabs();
83
84    });
85
```

Event handler definition

Event handler association

Initialization functions

Figure 26: Common JavaScript file sections.

3.1.2 Exceptional files

Most of the files are very similar between each other, but there are some exceptions:

1. **irradiations.js**: This file is dedicated to a list page (irradiations page) just like the majority of IDM JS files, but it contains additional complexity. In contrast to the

other pages, it updates data live when irradiations are in beam. To update data live, it has to control the number of requests sent to the server. If more than one database request is sent at a time, race conditions occur and data is not saved correctly in the database. For this reason, only one request is sent at a time to update page live data. Also, if the user decides to perform an action (e.g. create an irradiation), the live data requests are stopped until this request is completed. User actions have priority over live data.

2. **utilities.js:** This file differs from the rest because it is a collection of helper functions used by the rest of JS files. An important function contained in the file is "formRequest". It is the standard method to communicate with the sever asynchronously. It manages server errors, server timeouts, callbacks, loaders and modal behavior.
3. **jquery.formset.js:** This file contains an external library which has been modified for IDM purposes. All the changes to the original library are signaled with comments in the file, and the original code is included in the comments in case the original functionality needs to be restored.

3.2 Cascade Styling Sheets

All styling files are referenced in the 'base.html' file. Besides the styling provided by libraries, there is one file containing all IDM-specific styling called "style.css".

4 Development

4.1 Project Management

JIRA[15] is the tool used for project management and documentation. Both bugs and improvements are stored in the application to monitor their progress and future reference.

Figure 27: IDM open JIRA issues.

The project is configured to tightly synchronize GitLab and JIRA. This is possible by enforcing every commit pushed to the repository is associated to a JIRA issue. Since JIRA and GitLab are linked together, every commit containing an issue code is automatically added as a comment in JIRA for reference. Commits without a JIRA issue code in their message are not accepted by the repository. With this configuration, it is not possible to commit a change to the repository without tracking it before via JIRA.

Figure 28: Example of automated GitLab commit comment in Jira.

JIRA also works as a progress monitoring tool. With its built-in reporting tools, it is possible to easily evaluate the activity of the project as well as the progress achieved.

Figure 29: JIRA cumulative flow diagram reporting tool. IDM backlog (orange), in progress (blue) and completed (purple) issues over project life time.

4.2 Testing

4.2.1 Automated Testing

The project currently has 250 automated tests which can be executed within 13 minutes. They represent a large portion of the project with 10.642 lines of code. In total there are four files which test data models, views, form and functionalities. The last type, functional tests, test the application through the graphical user interface with the help of a browser automation tool called Selenium. Functional tests test all, and not only, database-related actions available in IDM.

```
Creating test database for alias 'default'...
System check identified no issues (0 silenced).
.....
-----
Ran 220 tests in 551.166s

OK
Destroying test database for alias 'default'...
```

Figure 30: Example of IDM automated tests' successful execution.

Functional tests are the most time consuming tests. Therefore, as a rule of thumb, it is preferable to test the application using other kind of tests whenever possible.

Before the deployment of IDM to the test server, tests should be run to make sure everything is working as expected.

Automated tests make use of the defined fixtures to isolate their execution and avoid interference from other tests. This is the reason why the development environment uses an SQLite database, instead of a CERN Oracle database as in production. CERN Oracle databases are not suitable for automated testing, since the creation and deletion of databases is restricted, and therefore test isolation isn't possible.

4.2.2 User Experience Testing

Whenever new functionality is developed, it is recommendable to organize usability sessions with admin and/or non-admin users depending on the scope of the newly applied changes, to evaluate the application's user experience.

Usability sessions can be carried out remotely using video conference systems with the possibility of remote control. Sessions should be recorded for later analysis, and the feedback provided by users and the results of the recording analysis should be written as Jira issues for future development.

Usability sessions are useful for the development team to gain different perspectives of the application. So far there have been five different recorded usability sessions, and many high priority JIRA issues have been detected as a result of these sessions. For this reason, it is recommendable to continue this practice in the future.

4.3 Style Guides

For coding styleguides, the project uses as reference two Google styleguides [\[16\]](#) [\[17\]](#) for the JavaScript and Python code. The use of these styleguides has been very beneficial to increase the comprehension and uniformity of the code.

5 Future Work

As of November 2021, there are 63 JIRA issues open in IDM. This section will list the most relevant issues to be completed in the future. For a complete view of pending issues, detailed explanations are available in the IDM JIRA page.

- **Advanced filtering:** Currently IDM is capable of filtering elements in list pages, but with fixed query structures. It is a future plan for IDM to be able to perform advanced queries. Either designing a suited graphical interface or defining a simplified query language.
- **User space:** IDM users are registered in the application automatically when they login using CERN's SSO. Once the information is registered, it is only modifiable by administrators. In the future, IDM should enable non-admin users to edit their profile data. This space will also be needed to enable user specific time zones.
- **Background processing:** There are multiple actions in IDM which are time consuming, and are capable of exceeding timeout limits. Usually these actions involve multiple requests to external databases. The current approach to limit the length of these requests is to restrict the number of elements selected in an action. Although this system provides a temporary solution, the correct approach would be to process these requests in the background and inform users when they have been completed. This solution can be implemented once a user space capable of storing user notifications is available.
- **Form template structure:** To assure a consistent look in forms, a future task is to define a hierarchical template structure for forms, similar to the structure of list and detail pages.
- **Form page validation:** Currently all form validation occurs after its final submission. A future task requested by users is to include dynamic validation between form pages, to improve form's user experience.

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